

Fig. 1. Plot of optical density vs wavelength of iron-2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime complex at various pH values.

as $[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$. The reagent under investigation is a bidentate uninegative ligand. It forms a 1:1 complex with iron replacing two water molecules from the coordination sphere. It is also known from the conductance measurements that the complex is neutral, hence, assuming that iron in the complex is tripositive, one charge being neutralised by the oxime and the other two charges by the anionic ligands present in the medium, possibly OH^- , the formula of the complex is suggested as $[\text{FeL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{OH})_2]$.

Interferences: The interference of various ions associated with iron(III) in its ores, alloys, living systems and precipitated with it in analysis on the absorbancy of iron complex was studied. 10 ppm/50 ml of iron(III) in each case was treated with the reagent (4 ml, 0.1%) and known variable amounts of other ion. The pH was adjusted to 2.5 and optical densities were measured. Na and K ions have no effect on the absorbancy even when each ion was present upto 400 ppm. Mg^{2+} (100 ppm), Ca^{2+} (100 ppm), Sn^{2+} (90 ppm), Be^{2+} (100 ppm), Zn^{2+} (100 ppm), Mn^{2+} (85 ppm), U^{10}O_8 (60 ppm), Cr^{3+} (50 ppm), Sb^{3+} (50 ppm), As^{3+} (60 ppm), Ti^{4+} (50 ppm), Th^{4+} (55 ppm), Co^{2+} (7 ppm), Mo^{6+} (7 ppm), W^{6+} (7 ppm), Bi^{3+} (7 ppm), and V^{5+} (10 ppm) ions cause not more than 0.05% error in the determination of 10 ppm of iron when present in the amounts shown in brackets. Cu^{2+} and Zr^{4+} ions interfered by forming precipitates with the reagent.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Ruthenium(III) Using 6-Amino-5-nitroso-2,4-pyrimidinediol and Pyridine

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A number of pyrimidine derivatives have been recently introduced as reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of different matters¹. Ruthenium has been estimated spectrophotometrically with 6-amino-5-nitroso-2,4-pyrimidinediol² (6-ANP). The idea that the formation of the ternary complex can lead to better sensitivity than binary complex has motivated us to carry out its determination with 6-ANP and pyridine.

Experimental

The stock solution of Ru^{3+} was prepared by dissolving $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Koch Light, U.K.) in 1.0 N HCl. Solutions of primary ligand, 6-ANP (monosodium salt) and secondary ligand, pyridine were prepared in 0.1 N HCl. The pH of the solutions were adjusted with acetate buffer and dilute solutions of HCl and NaOH. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout the work.

Absorbance readings were taken with a Unicam SP-600 spectrophotometer. For pH measurement a Metrohm E-350 pH-meter was used.

Procedure: To a suitable aliquot of Ru^{III} solutions (containing 6 to 45 µg metal) sufficient excess of 6-ANP and pyridine solutions and 4.0 ml of acetate buffer were added and the pH adjusted around 3.0. The solution was heated on a steam bath for ~40 min to ensure full colour development. The solution was then cooled to room temperature and diluted to 10 ml. The absorbance was measured at 530 nm against a reagent blank. The ruthenium concentration was calculated by comparing the absorbance with a calibrated curves.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the solutions containing a fixed amount of Ru^{III} and different concentrations of 6-ANP and pyridine were recorded against reagent blank under various conditions. The reaction was slow at room temperature but when solutions were heated on a steam bath for 30 min the full colour developed. Further heating did not change the absorbances. Therefore, a development time of 40 min was adopted for further studies. The characteristics of the complex studied are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF Ru^{III} TERNARY COMPLEX

Characteristic	Ru ^{III} -complex
Colour	Red-max
$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	530
$\epsilon_{\max}$ (l mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	1.2×10^4
pH range for maximum absorbance	1.0–3.5
Reagents needed for full colour development	25 fold 6-ANP and 15 fold pyridine
Molar composition (metal-6-ANP)	1 : 2
Beer's law range (µg ml ⁻¹)	upto 5.5
Optimum range for determination (µg ml ⁻¹)	0.6–4.5
Standard deviation calculated from 10 determinations	0.002

The molar absorptivity of the ternary complex of the metal has been found to be more than its complex only with 6-ANP² (22500 l mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The ternary complex seems to have been stabilised by mixed ligation with pyridine.

Effect of diverse ions: In determination of 2 ppm of Ru^{III} the following ions were tolerated: Cl⁻, Br⁻, CH₃COO⁻ (5000); F⁻, NO₃⁻ (1000); oxalate, I⁻ (500); Cd^{II}, PO₄³⁻, citrate (200); SCN⁻ (100). Thiourea, NO₂⁻, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} interfere.

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Potassium *N*-(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinate as a Gravimetric Reagent for Thorium(IV)

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ALTHOUGH several reagents have been recommended for gravimetric determination of thorium, only a few are in the actual use¹. Thorium is generally estimated as ThO₂ through ignition of precipitates formed with ammonium hydroxide or oxalic acid. Prior removal of interfering elements is essential in all the cases. Although several other carboxylic acids and certain amines are also used for precipitation², the present report is the first instance of using a Schiff base as gravimetric reagent for thorium. The title reagent is found versatile in forming well-defined metal chelates with a variety of metal ions³. Its reaction with Th^{IV} is quantitative, and since the metal chelate formed is also insoluble in aqueous media, it is well-suited for determining thorium gravimetrically.

Experimental

Potassium *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinate (KH Nap : gly) was prepared as follows. Potassium hydroxide (0.56 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in hot methanol (30 ml), and after adding glycine (0.75 g, 0.01 mol), the mixture was stirred magnetically. When the mixture became homogeneous, a solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (1.72 g, 0.01 mol) in hot methanol (20 ml) was added to it. A yellow precipitate which separated out immediately, was filtered hot, washed three times with 10 ml portions of methanol, sucked dry, and then crystallised from hot methanol as yellow crystals (80%), m.p. 250°. The compound was characterised on the basis of its micro-analytical, and uv, ir and nmr spectral data³.

A freshly prepared 2% aqueous ethanolic (90% v/v) solution of the reagent was used for precipitating thorium. A stock solution of Th(NO₃)₄·5H₂O of known concentration (~5.5 g per dm³ of aqueous solution) was prepared and used. Parallel determinations of thorium using oxalic acid⁴ were also carried out for comparison.

Typical procedure for determining thorium using the Schiff base reagent was as follows. An aliquot (~25 ml) of stock solution was diluted to ~100 ml, and its pH adjusted to 4.0. To this solution, stirred and heated to ~80°, was added the reagent solution (~25 ml) till the formation of yellow precipitate ceased. Then 1 ml more of the reagent was added, and after heating on a water-bath for 5 min, the precipitated complex was collected on a Whatman no. 41 filter and washed with water containing 1% ethanol. The precipitate-